

Design of alkali activated foamy binders from Sicilian volcanic precursors

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, porous inorganic polymers were synthesized by alkaline activation of volcanic ash and ‘ghiarra’ paleosol using Al swarf and Al commercial powder as pore inducing agent. The Alkali Activated Foams (AAFs) were characterized in terms of mineralogy, macro- and microstructure, by synchrotron X-ray diffraction, electron microscopy, infrared spectroscopy, and X-ray computed microtomography. The obtained porous matrices show different microstructures; the size and extent of the pores vary according to the type, size and amount of the foaming agent and to the viscosity of the pastes. Addition of Al swarf to the volcanic ash based slurry generates expansion of the paste, whereas *ghiarra* based one do not expand due to a lower viscosity of the slurry. Moreover, results indicate that the Al addition procedure during the synthesis affects the pore characteristics: Al powder added directly to the volcanic ash-based slurry triggers an incipient pore nucleation, whereas AAFs prepared adding Al powder to the solid mix do not develop an extended pore network. Results of this research show that porosity can be efficiently tailored in volcanic based AAFs by regulating the amount and type of Al.

1. Introduction

The development of sustainable construction and building materials to reduce the environmental footprint in both manufacturing and operational phases is a key point in the global housing and construction industry, especially considering the mission of the EU on the green revolution and ecological transition. In the last decades, in response to the growing global concerns over CO₂ emissions from the construction sector, innovative materials known as Alkali Activated Materials (AAMs), have attracted the attention of the scientific community as alternative to Portland cements (PC) due to the considerable energy saving in their production [1,2]. In this scenario, the development of novel and green materials that efficiently contribute to reducing the energy consumption of buildings during the whole of their lifetime is therefore crucial.

AAMs, including the so called “geopolymers”, are inorganic materials obtained by mixing reactive aluminosilicate powders of both natural and synthetic origin (e.g. pozzolans, fly ash, granulated blast furnace slag, mine tailing, waste glass, etc.) with alkaline activators such as sodium hydroxides and/or sodium silicate solutions. When Si and Al

contents are properly balanced with the cations in the alkaline solutions, a reaction takes place and a material with good binding properties is obtained at room temperature [1,3]. Geopolymers are a specific subset of AAMs. They are composed by the highest Al and lowest Ca concentrations and the main reaction product is a 3D inorganic alkaline polymer, with a highly cross-linked, disordered pseudo-zeolitic structure [4]. The possibility to employ various industrial wastes (i.e. fly ash, metallurgical slags, glass wastes and residues of mining cultivation) and natural raw materials makes the AAMs suitable in the novel circular economy paradigm [5–10]. Both geopolymers and alkali-activated materials have applications in construction, such as producing concrete and other building materials. They have many performance advantages such as the early compressive strength and the great chemical and heat resistance [11,12]. Moreover, their microstructure can be modified by regulating the formula and processing of bulk components in order to obtain tailored micro- and meso-porosity for different valuable applications such as thermal [13] and acoustic insulation [14,15], fire-resistance materials [16,17], adsorbents [18,19] and pH regulators [20,21], catalysts or catalyst supports [22,23].

In fact, they are often compared to porous ceramics or glasses for the

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similar properties due to their inorganic structures [8]. The main difference remains in the manufacturing process, since porous ceramics and glasses requires higher temperatures than AAMs for their consolidation.

For all the above-mentioned applications, it is necessary to control the pore structure (shape, morphology, orientation, surface properties) as well as the texture, the total porosity, and the pore size distribution.

The most common synthesis route to produce alkali activated foams is the chemical foaming technique or direct foaming method. This is based on the addition of foaming agents to the slurry (i.e. silica fume, Al powder or peroxides) capable of *in situ* gas generation which is trapped during the hardening of the pastes [24–26]. Metallic Al is widely used in the lightweight concrete industry as a chemical foaming agent, due to its high reactivity that can easily generate H₂ gas when in contact with a strongly alkaline aqueous solution [17,27–29]. This reaction is sometimes inhibited by the presence of non-soluble layers that commonly protect the Al surface at ambient temperature [30]. However, alkaline solutions such as NaOH can catalyse the reaction of the Al with water allowing the generation of hydrogen [31,32].

Several studies making use of metallic Al as a foaming agent have demonstrated that porosity can be efficiently controlled and regulated [33,34]. It is therefore crucial to evaluate the impact of Al corrosion on the development of the porosity and on the properties of the binding skeleton, as well as on the geopolymerisation reaction, since each formulation has different physical properties and kinetics that governs the capability to retain gas.

In this work, the feasibility to prepare porous AAMs based on Sicilian low-cost materials has been assessed. To this purpose, volcanic products given by volcanic ash [35,36] and ‘*ghiara*’ paleosol from Mount Etna [37], plus pumice from Lipari Island [36,38] were employed as precursors. These materials are indeed very abundant in Sicily, especially the volcanic ash often emitted by Mount Etna in high volumes (>10⁵–10⁶ m³ per event - [39]) during the numerous paroxysmal events occurred in the last years [40]. The Etnean *ghiara* is a reddish loose material originating during effusive eruptions by the interaction between lava flows and exposed soils [37]. In past centuries, *ghiara* was widely employed in construction field for its reddish hue and the high pozzolanic activity; for the same reasons it has now raised the interest of the scientific community involved in the formulation and production of eco-friendly materials as alternative to the traditional ones for local restoration purposes. Pumice rocks, originating by the eruption of highly silicic magmas, were collected in dismissed quarries at Lipari island; this material is nowadays extracted from various sites in Italy such as the Vulsino and the Cimino–Vicano volcanic districts.

Original binders’ recipes for each volcanic precursors (ash, *ghiara* paleosol and pumice) were taken from previous studies [10,35,38] and hereafter modified in order to obtain porous materials. Two different types of metallic Al were employed as foaming agents: Al swarf from industrial processing and commercial Al “silver” powder, a commercial Al pigmented dust used for decoration, fine arts, restoration, coating and industrial uses. Alkali Activated Foams (AAFs) with different porosity were then prepared varying the type and the amount of aluminium. The obtained AAFs were analyzed in order to evaluate the effect of the employed Al types and amounts on the chemical, textural and microstructural features in the view of potential application such as acoustic and thermal insulation, thermal comfort, catalysis, adsorption and filtration. Hardened porous materials underwent mineralogical analysis by synchrotron X-ray diffraction, apparent density tests, Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Scanning Electron Microscopy coupled with X-rays Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (SEM/EDS), and X-ray computed microtomography.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Starting materials and alkali activated foam (AAFs) preparation

Etnean trachybasaltic volcanic ash [9,36], volcanic red paleosol named *ghiara* from Etnean quarries [37] and a Lipari rhyolite pumice (Aeolian Islands, Sicily, Italy) [38] were used as precursors for the synthesis of the AAFs.

First of all binders were prepared according to the recipes given in Refs. [10,35,38]. In particular, raw materials were mixed with small percentage of metakaolin (ARGICAL™ M – 1000 supplied by IMERYs, France) and activated with a solution of 8 M sodium hydroxide (Carlo Erba reagents s.r.l., Italy) and sodium silicate (molar ratio SiO₂/Na₂O = 3.3, Ingessil s.r.l., Italy). Details of the mixing proportion are reported in Table 1. All these AAMs were deeply characterized and the results have demonstrated a good chemical and mechanical properties [35,38,41,42] also in terms of durability when subjected to natural weathering exposure [9,43]. Afterward, foaming agents have been added to those formulation make porous AAFs.

Al swarf from industrial processing and Al commercial powder (“silver” metal powder, 56 μm) was used as the foaming agent. Al swarf was washed in acetone in order to eliminate oil and impurities and then sieved to take only the finest fraction (<75 μm). The amount of the foaming agent and the mixing procedure was defined by a trial and error approach. Details of samples preparation are shown in Table 1. AAFs were prepared following two procedures:

- 1) The foaming agent (Al swarf/powder) was mixed with the solid precursors before mixing with an alkaline solution;
- 2) The foaming agent (Al swarf/powder) was added directly to the slurry at the end of mixing and stirred gently for a few seconds.

Pastes were poured into cubic plastic moulds of 4 × 4 × 4 cm and filled to 2 cm-high in order to allow the expansion of the material. All samples were cured at 25 ± 3 °C in sealed vessels for 24 h to ensure 99% of relative humidity.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Specific gravity

Specific gravity (SG) was determined for each specimen by means of a hydrostatic balance. Before the measurements, samples were heated at 100 °C for 24 h to ensure a dry weight and then sealed with paraffin. The measurements have been carried out at room temperature condition.

2.2.2. Synchrotron X-ray powder diffraction analysis

XRPD measurements on the geopolymers and starting materials were performed at Elettra Synchrotron facility (Trieste, Italy) at the MCX beamline [44,45]. The powder samples were packed in borosilicate capillary with a diameter of 500 μm and collected in transmission mode, in the 2–65° 2θ angular range, 0.01 step-size and 1 s of counting time. Before the XRPD measurements, 10 wt% of a standard corundum powder (NIST code 676a) was added to each sample to perform the quantitative phase analysis (QPA) and calculate the amorphous phase [45]. Data were collected at room temperature using a monochromatic wavelength of 1.0324 Å (12 keV), on a 4-circle Huber goniometer equipped with a scintillation detector. The phase identification was performed using HighScorePlus software while the quantitative analysis were obtained by the Rietveld method using GSASII software [46]. The quality of Rietveld refinements was evaluated on the basis of both the visual observations of observed and calculated patterns and the comparison of the values of discrepancy indices as the weight profile R-factor, whose values resulted lower than 15% as index of an adequate refinement [47].

Table 1
Details of synthesis parameters and specific weight of the geopolymers.

Sample	Precursor	Precursor/MK (weight ratio)	L/S ratio of the slurry	SS/SH (wt %)	Type of Al	Foaming agent on the slurry (wt.%)	Specific weight (g/cm ³)
1CEN	Volcanic ash	80/20	0.32	1.67	Al swarf added to solid mix	4.2	1.30
2CEN	Volcanic ash	80/20	0.32	1.67	Al swarf added to solid mix	0.9	1.60
3CEN	Volcanic ash	80/20	0.32	1.67	Al fine powder added to solid mix	0.2	1.81
4CEN	Volcanic ash	80/20	0.32	1.67	Al fine powder added to slurry	0.2	1.08
5GHI	Ghiara paleosoil	80/20	0.32	1.67	Al swarf added to solid mix	4.8	1.26
6POM	Pumice	70/30	0.61	1.19	Al swarf added to solid mix	1.4	1.06

2.2.3. Infrared spectroscopy

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy in Attenuated Total Reflection (FTIR-ATR) was performed on the powdered samples by means of a Thermo Fisher Scientific 380 Infrared spectrometer (Nicolet). The data were recorded at room temperature and the spectra were calculated by Fourier transformation of 64 interferometer scans in a range of wavenumbers between 400 and 4000 cm⁻¹ with 4 cm⁻¹ resolution.

2.2.4. Scanning Electron Microscopy

Back-scattered electron (BSE), secondary electron (SE) images and chemical analyses on geopolymeric samples were collected with a TESCAN Vega-LMU scanning electron microscope equipped with an EDAX Neptune XM4-60 microanalyzer operating by energy dispersive system. The microanalyzer is characterized by an ultrathin Be window coupled with an EDAX WDS LEXS (wavelength dispersive low energy X-ray spectrometer) calibrated for light elements. Operating conditions were set at 20 kV accelerating voltage and ca 8 nA beam current for obtaining high resolution BSE images and 20 kV accelerating voltage and 0.2 nA beam current for analysing major element abundances.

2.2.5. Computed microtomography and image analysis

The three-dimensional (3D) characterization of the synthesized samples was performed using a Bruker SKYSCAN 1174 X-ray computed microtomography scanner operating in cone beam geometry. Samples were cut in cubic shape with a lateral size of ~10–15 mm. The X-ray source was a sealed air-cooled X-ray tube operating in a voltage range of 20–50 kV. The used detector was a 1304 × 1024 pixels digital X-ray camera coupled to a P43 scintillator screen. The spatial resolution was set at 6.2 μm/pixel, yielding a maximum field of view of ~51.32 mm². For each experiment, 1800 projections were collected with an exposure time of 10 s/projection at an angle step of 0.1° over a total scan angle of 180°. The total time for each acquisition was 5 h. Reconstruction of the images was performed by the InstaRecon® reconstruction engine applying the modified Feldkamp algorithm [48]. Three-dimensional renderings were elaborated using the commercial software VGStudio MAX 3.0.

Reconstructed 3D volumes are given by greyscale stacks of images (slices) where heavy components are identified by bright colours and light phases and voids have dark colours. The obtained 3D volumes were processed in order to extract the pore phase, identified by the dark/black voxels (3D pixels) of the greyscale slices. The image processing was performed by extracting, from each stack of slices, a volume of interest (VOI) that was further processed in order to retrieve the pore phase. From greyscale colour VOIs, binary (black and white) images of the sole pore phase were extracted by manual thresholding using the Fiji free-ware software [49]. The obtained binary pore images were then analyzed using the Pore3D software library [50] for retrieving:

- porosity (volume of pores/volume of VOI)
- total number of pores (#/mm³)
- volume of each pore (mm³)

- morphologic descriptors of pores.

The degree of connectivity (connectivity density, CD) of the pore network was calculated via a skeletonization approach, using the LKC algorithm [51]. The CD values are calculated as a scalar value representing the number of redundant connections normalized to the total volume *V*. It is computed as $(1 - X_V)/V$ where $X_V = (n - b)$, being *n* the number of pores and *b* the number of node-to-node branches [50].

3. Results

3.1. Macroscopic observation and specific weight

The resulting hardened samples are shown in Fig. 1, while results of specific weight measurement are shown in Table 1 and Fig. 2. The measured specific weight varies from 1.06 to 1.82 g/cm³ 1CEN, 2CEN, 5GHI and 6POM were prepared by adding swarf Al directly to solid precursors in different percentages (Table 1). 1CEN ($\rho = 1.30$ g/cm³) and 5GHI ($\rho = 1.26$ g/cm³), prepared with Al swarf in the mixture >4 wt %, show large porous matrix. 1CEN sample swelled up, denoting an expansion of the paste while 5GHI did not significantly increase in volume (Fig. 1). Reducing the Al percentage as in the 2CEN ($\rho = 1.6$ g/cm³, Al swarf <1 wt%), a porous matrix is formed but also in this case the sample did not expand. 6POM ($\rho = 1.06$ g/cm³) sample, with only the 1.4 wt% of Al swarf in the mixture, shows a porous matrix and an expansion similar to 1CEN. Al fine powder (0.2 wt%) was used as foaming agent in the volcanic ash-based samples 3CEN ($\rho = 1.82$ g/cm³) and 4CEN ($\rho = 1.08$ g/cm³). In the former, the aluminium was mixed with the solids prior to the alkaline activation, in the latter the Al was added directly to the slurry. As a result, 3CEN did not show a foaming reaction whereas in 4CEN the reaction took place, with evident bubble development (Fig. 1).

3.2. Characteristic of the binding skeleton

3.2.1. X-ray diffraction analysis

The synchrotron radiation allowed us to obtain XRD patterns with a high signal/noise ratio in order to characterize the mineralogical phases after the reaction with foaming agents occurred during the alkaline activation process, and to compare them with the corresponding precursors. Fig. 3a and b, displays the XRD patterns and the mineralogical phases detected through the qualitative analysis, while the detailed results of quantitative analysis obtained by the Rietveld method are listed in Table 2.

The volcanic ash raw material (CEN_P, Fig. 3a) shows the typical trachybasalt mineral assemblage of Mt. Etna products (Table 2), given by abundant feldspar (i.e., plagioclase 54.84 wt%), pyroxene (augite 18.39 wt%), subordinate forsteritic olivine (3.91 wt%) and Fe-oxide as accessory phase (magnetite 0.21 wt%), together with the amorphous phase (22.65 wt%) given by volcanic glass. The volcanic ash based AAFs samples (Fig. 3 a) exhibit the same assemblage plus quartz due to the metakaolin added to the mixture. The amorphous phase of AAFs

Fig. 1. Macroscopic geopolymer sample after 28 days.

Fig. 2. Specific weight of the samples vs. amount of foaming agent added during the AAFs synthesis.

increases with respect to the raw material (from 22.65 to 62.79 wt% averaged value) due to the partial dissolution of the original minerals during the alkali activation and because of the addition of metakaolin (Table 2) that contributes to the gel formation.

The *ghiara* GHI_P raw material (Fig. 3b) shows a mineralogical composition similar to that of volcanic ash, since its origin is related to the chemico-physical transformations occurring during the covering of volcanic paleosoil by an active lava flow [37]. In fact, GHI_P displays bytownitic and anorthitic plagioclase (55.27 wt%), pyroxene (10.37 wt%), fosteritic olivine (2.95 wt%) and hematite (1.05 wt%); the amorphous phase reaches the 30.36 wt%.

The corresponding 5GHI AAF material (Fig. 3b) shows a reduction of all the crystal phases with respect to the precursor; in particular feldspars decrease from 55.27 wt% in the raw material to 24.45 wt% in the geopolymer (Table 2). This dissolution is balanced by a large increase of the amorphous phase in the 5GHI AAF (62.84 wt%). The presence of a small amount of quartz (1.58 wt%) is due to the metakaolin contribution.

Both pumice precursor and foamy sample (Fig. 3b) exhibit a considerable amorphous amount (91.45 and 94.41 wt% in the foamy sample and precursor, respectively), due to the genesis process of the raw material by quenching of a crystal-free, SiO₂-rich magma [38]. The few accessory phases found are: plagioclase, quartz and anatase (Table 2).

3.2.2. FTIR-ATR analysis

Fig. 4a, c and d show the spectra of the analyzed samples in the region from 400 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹. The range of 900–1200 cm⁻¹ in FTIR spectra is attributed to the main Si–O–T band (T = tetrahedral Si or Al) which generally carries some useful information about the geopolymer formation kinetics and on the participation of key species in gel network [52]. Overall, the position of the Si–O–T stretching band is detected in the range from 966 cm⁻¹ to 978 cm⁻¹ regions.

Fig. 4b shows a portion of the FTIR-ATR spectra in the range of 800–1250 cm⁻¹ of volcanic ash-based foam geopolymers. Regardless of the type and the amount of Al, the position of the Si–O–T band is the same for the 1CEN (4.2 Al wt%), 2CEN (0.9 Al wt%) and 4CEN (0.2 Al Wt.%) at 973–974 cm⁻¹. On the other hand, some differences are revealed by the intensities of the main band: sample 1CEN, containing the highest amount of Al, shows the lowest intensity, while 3CEN, having lower amount of Al, shows the highest intensity.

A weak hump around 850–900 cm⁻¹ has been also revealed in all samples with Al. It can be assigned to the Al–OH stretching vibration, as found in metakaolin based geopolymers [53] or to the Si–OH bending vibration. The presence of Si–OH can lead to a decrease in the degree of condensation [54]. The presence of carbonates, due to the atmospheric carbonation [55], is evident only for 6POM and is identified by the bands at 1400 cm⁻¹ (CO₃²⁻ stretching vibrations) and at 875 cm⁻¹ (NaHCO₃). Water participation in the reaction is identified in bending vibration at around 1660 cm⁻¹ and symmetric and asymmetric vibration at around 3500 cm⁻¹.

3.2.3. Scanning electron microscopy

The microstructure of AAFs and the gel morphology and composition were studied and compared by SEM-EDX. In addition, SEM allowed us to gain deeper insights into the geopolymer matrices between the pores. Images from the fractured surface of the samples after 28 days of curing are shown in Figs. 5–7. All samples show unreacted particles as confirmed by the XRD pattern. Fig. 5 compares SE-micrographs of 1CEN and 4CEN, prepared using different types and amounts of Al. At low magnifications (71–89 ×, Fig. 5), the presence of heterogeneous porosity is evident. At higher magnification (ca. 1.15–1.39 k ×, Fig. 5) the gel microstructure and the compactness of the matrices are similar. Some unreacted particles have been detected in both samples, as also confirmed by XRD analyses (Fig. 3) and they appear embedded in the amorphous matrices. The latter is clearly visible in Fig. 5 (at ca. 2.3–4.88 k × of magnification). The matrix displays amorphous features, with the distinctive granular aspect of the geopolymeric gel, represented by ultra-fine (sub-micrometric) particles confined into isolated elements and partially bonded together.

Backscattered electron images of the 1CEN sample have been collected in order to evaluate the effect of the Al swarf on the matrix composition (Fig. 6). At 504 × of magnification, the matrix exhibits light

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of raw precursors and AAFs (Ant: anatase-code: amcsd 0011765; Crn: corundum-code: 1000032; Ol: olivine-code: 9000166; Ox: oxides/hydroxides-code: 9005840 and 9000139; Pl: plagioclase (bytownite-code: 2108237, and albite-code: 1556998, anorthite-code: 1000034; Px: pyroxene-code: 1200006; Qtz: quartz-code: amcsd 0000789).

and dark portions, recognizable also at higher magnification ($1.30k \times$, Fig. 6b). EDX spot analyses revealed a compositional variability (spectra of the inset b1 and b2). Both samples are composed of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and

Na_2O typical of an aluminosilicate N-A-S-H gel composition, with K_2O , CaO and Fe_2O_3 in minor amount. Local enrichment in Al_2O_3 content is revealed in the dark areas ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ molar ratio of 2.1) at the expenses of SiO_2 which is higher in the light areas ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ molar ratio of 3.2). Furthermore, small differences in the gel composition are evidenced by EDX analysis (Fig. 6c, inset c1). The presence of a higher amount of CaO (CaO/SiO_2 molar ratio of 1.3) in some portions of the matrix denotes also the possible formation of (N,C)-A-S-H gel in which a partial replacement of Na^+ ions by Ca^{2+} ions occurs due to the contribution of CaO hydration.

BSE images of 4CEN and 5GHI (Fig. 7) show details of the Al particles that did not dissolve during the alkali activation process and they were partially corroded by the alkaline environment forming micropores around their edges (Fig. 7b).

3.3. X-ray microtomography and pore analysis

Reconstructed axial slices of 4CEN and 5GHI samples (Fig. 8 a and b respectively) confirm the presence of a heterogeneous distribution of pores and of undissolved Al. Fig. 9 shows 3D renderings of VOIs from selected AAFs obtained using Al powder (4CEN) and Al swarf (5GHI and 6 POM) as foaming agents.

The porosity of the investigated samples spans from 11.73 to 56.5 vol % (Table 3). Pores have volume in the order of 10^{-6} to 10 mm^3 , with average values between 2×10^{-4} and $9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^3$. The high values of the standard deviation of the average volumes reported in Table 3 remark the large variability of single pore sizes. The morphology of pores is similar for all the samples, with average values in the range of 0.77–0.84, indicating that voids diverge from a spherical shape. However, pore distribution is isotropic in all samples, as testified by the low Elongation (<0.06) and the high Isotropy ($I > 0.88$) indexes (Table 3).

In order to investigate in detail, the pore distribution within the samples, the pore number distribution (PND) and the pore volume distribution (PVD) were calculated for each sample (Fig. 10). The PND curves for all samples, with the exception of 2CEN, indicate that the majority of the pores has volume peaked at 10^{-5} mm^3 . The PVD curves (Fig. 10b) show a similar trend, with different behaviour of 3CEN. This sample in fact shows a bimodal trend peaked at 10^{-4} and 1 mm^3 . The rest of the AAFs displays that the greatest part of the porosity ($>95\%$) is given by large voids (between 1 and 10 mm^3). This trend is confirmed by the number density values (Table 3), indicating that only sample 3CEN has a value higher than 500 pores/ mm^3 , whereas the rest of the suite ranges between 43 and 87 pores/ mm^3 .

Volcanic-ash based AAFs show different pore distributions: pore number fraction diagrams (Fig. 10) of 1CEN and 4CEN are clearly peaked at 10^{-5} mm^3 , whereas 2CEN is peaked at 10^{-6} . The same curve for the 3CEN sample, although peaking at 10^{-5} mm^3 , shows a shift toward the 10^{-6} vol size, indicating an intermediate behaviour. These curves thus evidence that 2CEN and 3CEN have a higher number of small pores compared to 1CEN and 4CEN. The pore volume fraction diagram (Fig. 10) partially reflects this feature, being 1CEN, 2CEN and 4CEN peaked at 10 mm^3 . The 3CEN sample, on the contrary, shows a

Table 2

Mineralogical results (in wt.%) obtained by XRD analysis with Rietveld Method. The refinement quality was evaluated on the basis of the weight profile R-factor.

	Ant	Ol	Ox	Pl	Px	Qtz	Amorph.	R (%)
CEN_P	–	3.91	0.21	54.84	18.39	–	22.65	8
CEN1	–	2.06	0.31	27.45	9.49	4.85	55.83	6.31
CEN2	–	4.8	0.08	21.66	6.85	4.76	61.85	6.15
CEN3	–	2.48	0.14	18.65	7.11	2.76	68.85	5.45
CEN4	–	2.52	0.1	19.82	6.2	6.72	64.63	6.09
GHI_P	–	2.95	1.05	55.27	10.37	–	30.36	7.97
GHI5	–	2.52	0.51	24.45	8.1	1.58	62.84	6.89
PUM_P	–	–	–	5.11	–	0.44	94.45	5.75
PUM6	0.86	–	–	1.74	–	6	91.41	4.92

Ant: anatase; Ol: olivine; Ox: oxides/hydroxides; Pl: plagioclase; Px: pyroxene; Qtz: quartz; Amorph: amorphous.

Fig. 4. FTIR-ATR spectra of a) volcanic ash-based AAFs (coloured line); b) baseline-subtracted FTIR-ATR spectra in the 800–1250 cm^{-1} region of volcanic ash-based AAFs (coloured curves); c) *ghiara*-based-AAFs (red line); d) pumice-based AAFs (blue line); Respective no-foamy samples (black curves taken from Refs. [8,36]), are reported in each graph for comparison. For the interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. SEM images of foamy samples at different magnifications. a-c) 1CEN sample; d-f) 4CEN sample. Scale bars and magnifications are shown in the images.

bimodal trend with ~ 50 vol% of the void phase given by $0.1\text{--}1$ mm^3 pores and the other ~ 50 vol% constituted by smaller ($<10^{-2}$ mm^3) and isolated pores.

The 1CEN and 2CEN AAFs show high porosity which can be related in the first place to the amount of the foaming agent (4.2 and 0.9 wt%, respectively). The 3CEN sample shows the lowest porosity of the investigated AAFs suite and was synthesized by adding 0.2 wt% fine Al powder to the solid mix. AAFs obtained with pumice and *ghiara* show the same pore distribution and amount of volcanic ash-based ones (Fig. 10).

4. Discussions

The impact of Al on the multiscale porosity development of volcanic-based AAFs and the structural properties of the final binders are here investigated. Most of the studies conducted on geopolymer foams which makes use of Al as a foaming agent have demonstrated that the final porosity depends on several factors, such as the amount and type of Al, its oxidation state, the SS/SH ratio of the alkaline solution, the viscosity and setting time of the pastes and temperature of the curing [53,56,57]. The results of the present study highlight how all these factors affect the porosity of volcanic-based AAFs.

Fig. 6. BSE-EDX analyses of 1CEN sample at different magnification. Scale bars and magnifications are shown in the images.

Fig. 7. BSE-EDX analyses of a) 4CEN sample; b) 5GHI sample. Scale bars and magnifications are shown in the images.

Macroscopic observation indicates that when the extent of Al oxidation is complemented by a rapid setting of the paste, the result is an expansion of the material with the formation of the foam, whereas if the oxidation increases without the setting of paste, the generated gas escapes during mixing [53]. This is clearly shown by 1CEN and 5GHI samples. Although they contain higher Al swarf content with respect to the other samples (4.2 and 4.8 wt% respectively) and exhibit similar low specific weight (1.30 and 1.26 g/cm³), 5GHI does not expand. In general, *ghiara*-based pastes show higher viscosity with respect to the volcanic ash-based ones and the reason can be found in their mineralogical composition [37]. Even if *ghiara* based geopolymers have shown good cementitious properties when consolidated, they show lower workability of the pastes and lower versatility of the formulation with respect to the volcanic ash [35,43]. On the contrary, an evident correlation between the amount of Al swarf used for the AAFs and the porosity development in samples with the same recipe is displayed by 1CEN and 2CEN. In fact, reducing the Al percentage as in the 2CEN sample (Al swarf <1 wt%), a porous matrix forms but the sample does not expand as in the case of 1CEN. In the case of 6POM, lower Al swarf with respect to 1CEN and 5GHI is required to develop porosity (Table 1). This can be due to the diverse SS/SH = 1.19 ratio of this mixture, lower than that used for all the others (SS/SH = 1.67). In the case of 6POM, the gas released is

related to the higher NaOH content of the solution influencing the Al reaction [57]. In fact, it is known that alkaline solutions like sodium hydroxide act as a catalyst for the Al reaction accelerating the corrosion in water, whereas sodium silicate is an effective inhibitor of aluminium corrosion in alkaline systems [56]. Varying the ratios of these two activators is therefore possible to control the foaming reaction, reducing the Al dosage. However, caution must be taken in changing the silica modulus (SiO₂/Na₂O) of the solution, since it impacts on the geopolymerisation reaction and on the properties of the binding skeleton [58–61].

From the mineralogical point of view, X-ray synchrotron diffraction results evidence an overall a quite homogeneity among each type of sample due to the same nature of the volcanic aluminosilicate sources. The difference in terms of crystals and the amorphous amount is generally constant between precursors and foamy samples. The higher crystallinity is observable in the raw materials, whereas amorphous phases dominate in the non-foamy and foamy samples. No new crystalline phases (e.g. zeolites or carbonates) appear after the geopolymerisation reactions [35,43].

In order to investigate the Al reaction in the alkali environment and its effect on the geopolymeric matrices, the FTIR-ATR technique was used to investigate the structure of the foamy samples formulated in this

Fig. 8. Reconstructed 1304×1304 pixels axial slices of 4CEN (a) and 5GHI (b) samples. Dark phases are pores (green boxes) whereas the Al phase is identified by the bright objects. The intermediate grey constituting largest volume of both samples is given by the matrix. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

work with non-foamy ones designed with the same recipe and described in previous works [9,35,38]. Comparing the FTIR-ATR spectra of foamy and non-foamy samples (Fig. 4a–d) a shift is observable towards a lower wavenumber in the position of the Si–O–T band for all foamy samples except for *ghiara*-based ones (Fig. 4c). The shift of the main Si–O–T band toward 950 cm^{-1} is associated with the occurrence of the bending vibration of Al–OH. Generally, an increase in the amount of Al, which participate in the gel formation, leads to a shift toward the lower wavenumber of this band, at least in the early stage of the geopolymer reaction process [52,62,63]. As in fly ash-based geopolymer systems [52,55], also here the presence of Al in the geopolymer mixtures shifts the Si–O–T asymmetric stretch band to lower wavenumbers (from 978 cm^{-1} for non-foamy samples up to 971 cm^{-1} for 3CEN), even though

there is no correlation between the increase of the Al content and the shift of this band (Fig. 4a and b). However, 3CEN does not develop a porosity as its equivalent 4CEN and is very similar to the original non-foamy sample. This change is certainly related to the different preparation method of the foam with the fine Al powder added to the solid precursors in the case of 3CEN, and consequently the reaction of Al with the water of the system does not occur. On the other side, when Al fine powder is added to the slurry, it most likely takes part in the gel reaction, conditioning also the gel structure as explained later by microstructure analysis. Similarly, the pumice-based foamy sample (6POM, Fig. 4c) displays a shift of the main Si–O–T band towards lower values (from 974 cm^{-1} to 966 cm^{-1}) with respect to the non-foamy one, denoting a possible change of the gel structure due to the presence of Al in the mixture. FTIR-ATR spectra of both *ghiara* foamy and non-foamy samples do not show significant differences in the position of the Si–O–T band. Even though the amount of the Al swarf in the mixtures is the highest of the sample set (4.8 wt%), and the gas expansion occurs, this sample exhibits the same pore amount of 1CEN (see section 4.1). Still, the expansion is less pronounced and the aluminum is not completely consumed by the reaction, being visible to the naked eye. When aluminum is completely dissolved by the reaction it is integrated in the geopolymer gel, as shown by the EDX chemical data (see Fig. 6) and by the shift of the main aluminum-silicate band to lower wavenumbers. As reported by Ref. [64] the position of the main Si–O–T band is an indication of the extent of Al contribution in geopolymeric gels. The availability of Al in the mix can increase the formation of the amorphous aluminosilicate gel phase [55,65] and the amount of Al in the geopolymeric gel network modifies the distribution of length and angles of the main band, shifting it to lower wavenumber [66].

Furthermore, the absence of sodium carbonates in all the volcanic-ash and *ghiara*-based foamy samples can be related to the increase in Al amount that limits the excess Na^+ remaining unreacted and is responsible for the efflorescence formation [67]. Although the L/S ratio is similar in all samples except for 6POM, the intensities of the 3500 cm^{-1} bands for 1CEN, 2CEN and 4CEN are lower than those of 3CEN and of the non-foamy samples. This fact could be related to the water consumption due to the heat produced by the reaction of Al and alkaline solution during the first stage of the hydrolysis reaction of geopolymerisation [33].

Microstructural analyses carried out by means of SEM-EDS and by micro-tomography demonstrates that a lower amount of Al powder (4CEN) results in spherical pores more uniformly distributed with respect to those of samples formulated using Al swarf (such as 1CEN). At this scale, the Al addition does not negatively affect the microstructure development of the binding skeleton (Figs. 5 and 6 a-c). Whether Al swarf or powder is used, it may not be consumed entirely by the reaction remaining clearly visible to the naked eye in the case of coarse fragments and observable at the microscale when powdered (cfr. Fig. 7 a,b).

The results of micro-tomography support those obtained by SEM-EDS: undissolved Al is revealed in the samples 4CEN and 5 GHI (Fig. 8a and b) and the dimension of the pores is related to the particle size of the Al foaming agent. Pores are visibly much bigger with Al swarf, while smaller pores developed when using Al fine powder. Homogenous gel distribution within the paste matrix results in a better compaction and in the formation of smaller pores (Figs. 7 and 8 and Table 3). Al swarf added to mixtures lead to an incipient pore formation with coalescence due to abundant gas release as in the case of 5GHI [68]. The Pore Volume Fraction Distribution indicates for 1CEN, 2CEN and 4CEN an incipient pore nucleation and growth, with the developing of an extended network of voids that form continuous pore phases, given by single or few large pores with a millimetric size that constitute $>90\%$ of the total void phase of the sample. The 3CEN sample, on the contrary, does not show pores larger than 1 mm^3 and displays a larger number of pores comprised between 10^{-5} and 10^{-2} mm^3 . The comparison between 3CEN and 4CEN samples, obtained with the same Al type and amount, suggests that different foaming can be induced by varying the method in

Fig. 9. Renderings of the imaged VOIs of selected investigated samples and isosurface renderings of the corresponding pore phase. Size of each VOI is given in [Table 3](#).

Table 3

Results of 3D analysis on representative Volumes of Interest (VOIs) of the samples.

Sample	1CEN	2CEN	3CEN	4CEN	5GHI	6POM
VOI size (voxels)	356 × 379 × 928	468 × 744 × 800	430 × 516 × 987	670 × 668 × 986	912 × 790 × 1005	632 × 714 × 793
VOI volume (mm ³)	29.84	66.38	52.19	105.17	172.57	85.28
<i>Pores analysis</i>						
Number of pores	2608	18196	27452	6912	10482	3719
Number density (mm ⁻³)	87.40	274.12	526.00	65.72	60.74	43.61
Porosity (vol%)	42.70	39.37	11.64	52.09	56.49	41.86
Euler char. (mm ⁻³)	60.01	232.30	395.76	31.04	-42.53	13.94
Int. Mean Curv. (mm ⁻²)	41.32	98.92	226.19	68.38	28.73	23.91
Spec. Surf. (mm ⁻¹)	5.30	5.59	8.42	8.07	8.70	4.13
<i>Anisotropy analysis</i>						
Elongation	0.033	0.033	0.031	0.027	0.063	0.019
Isotropy	0.889	0.887	0.935	0.954	0.927	0.885
<i>Morphologic analysis</i>						
Volume (mm ³)	0.005	0.001	0.000	0.008	0.009	0.010
Min. Axis (mm)	0.238	0.181	0.016	0.634	0.946	0.568
Max. Axis (mm)	0.016	0.007	0.008	0.021	0.009	0.021
Sphericity	0.021	0.016	0.013	0.027	0.012	0.029
Aspect ratio	0.057	0.036	0.040	0.063	0.041	0.061
	0.055	0.049	0.042	0.064	0.035	0.061
	0.775	0.843	0.789	0.792	0.784	0.782
	0.147	0.268	0.198	0.123	0.157	0.144
	0.211	0.099	0.114	0.256	0.154	0.244
	0.175	0.143	0.139	0.195	0.159	0.203
<i>Skeleton analysis</i>						
Conn. density (mm ⁻³)	24.06	22.50	37.28	22.85	113.07	27.87

In bold the standard deviation; for a complete description of the meaning of each parameter the reader is referred to Ref. [50].

which the foaming agent is added. Fine powder Al addition to the solid mix (3CEN) does not generate porosity, and the porosity encountered is that typical of a geopolymeric matrices, whereas its addition to the slurry (4CEN), even if in a lower amount, triggers a more incipient pore nucleation with porosity reaching >50 vol% in the finite product even at low foaming agent amount.

These results suggest that porosity does not depend exclusively on the foaming agent amount, but high porosity can be achieved also by a low % of Al, depending on the particle size of the foaming agent, the mix design of the binder (i.e. SS/SH ratio, L/S ratio, viscosity and setting time), and the preparation methods (mixed with a solid mix or added to the slurry). Depending on the final application of the AAF materials, pore size distribution and morphology can have a positive or negative effect on the technical properties. As an example, the irregular shape of the voids with a wide pore size distribution, which can form an interconnected network, could lead to a significant sound wave dissipation within the foam matrix [69,70]. On the other hand, circular and homogeneously distributed pores are desirable to improve the insulating properties [13,70].

Fig. 10. Bubbles size distributions: a) fraction of the number of pores having a given size; b) fraction of the porosity determined by pores having a given volume.

5. Conclusive remarks

In this work, metallic Al swarf and Al commercial powder have been successfully used as foaming agents without any thermal curing, for volcanic precursors-based AAFs formulation. The type and amount of the blowing agent, together with the mixing procedure, the viscosity of the slurry, setting time and composition strongly influence the pore development and therefore the properties of foamy materials.

The results of this investigation can be resumed as follows:

- The addition of Al fine powder to the solid mix (i.e. in volcanic-ash based AAFs) does not trigger gas release and pore development, while the addition of the same type and amount of Al in the slurry favors the gas expansion and the formation of an extended pore network. Al swarf added to the solid mix always leads the porosity development, whose extent is dependent on its amount.
- The increase of the NaOH/SS ratio enhances the Al corrosion, reducing the amount needed to form pores (i.e. pumice-based AAF).
- The setting time of the slurry is an important parameter for the foaming process and can influence the regularity, porosity, pore distribution, pores diameter, etc. of the foam structure. Fast hardening traps the gas within the geopolymer that develops coalesced pores, whereas a slower hardening rate allows the gas to escape, with the formation of a less extended pore network.

The lower extent of salts formation in the sample with aluminium powder indicates that consumption of some sodium hydroxide catalyst by the aluminium reaction can protect the geopolymer paste from the extensive carbonation. Homogenous gel distribution within the paste matrix results in a better connectivity of unreacted particles and better compaction of the paste, which in turn results in lower extent of large pores in samples 2CEN, 3CEN and 4CEN.

Since the gel network is the skeleton of AAFs materials, the pore size and connectivity are crucial factors in the overall strength of the porous materials and its durability. Further studies are therefore needed to better control the pore architecture and to investigate the mechanical and physical properties of volcanic based AAFs.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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